

Ontology-Based Systems Engineering for Traceability in Formal Methods

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Abstract. For highly automated AI-based systems, traceability is essential in increasing chances of a successful type approval. In basic terms, traceability ensures that any generated artifact can be traced back to its origin, linking, e.g., implementation and design models to requirements and requirements to stakeholder rationales. Due to aspirations of deploying more complex automated systems in ever-growing operational domains, traceability becomes harder to establish: Here, any model generated during engineering does not only link against its predecessor models, but also against a model of the system’s environment – an ontology. Ontology-based systems engineering (OBSE), a recently proposed method, acknowledges this fact by viewing ontologies as a central engineering artifact. While prior work has given a conceptual overview of the general approach, we are not aware of an examination of its positive impact on formal methods. Our presentation does a first step by connecting the models of a simplified formal methods workflow to a central ontology. Thereby, the output of verification tools becomes interpretable in the context of a unified environment model, which connects formal methods to prior engineering steps, such as discussions on semantics arising during requirements engineering. This link increases traceability and, potentially, the trust put in formal methods when used for a product’s type approval. To illustrate our thoughts, the presentation takes a dive into the challenge of ensuring traffic rule adherence in automated driving systems.

As the foundation of our proposed presentation, let us assume the following simple and prototypical formal methods workflow:

- (1) requirements in natural language are written down,
- (2) requirements are formalized,
- (3) a system is implemented against these requirements,
- (4) a system model is built (manually or automatically), capturing the behavior of the system and its possible inputs, and
- (5) a verification tool examines whether the system model is compliant to the formalized requirements.

For complex systems in open contexts, steps (1) to (4) typically encounter an *ontology* – a (formal) model of a domain conceptualization. This holds, e.g., for automated driving systems (ADSs) in intricate urban environments [5]. Such an ontology is highly complex, changes often, and must incorporate views of stakeholders of different domains along the development process, all with diverse conceptualizations (such as legal experts, society, and engineers).

Fig. 1. Formal models for requirements R and systems S generally relying on ontologies O_R and O_S , without an ontology-centric approach. Standard arrows indicate derivation steps to retrieve formal requirements \hat{R} and system models \hat{S} . Dashed edges represent model dependencies.

Figure 1 shows the previously introduced process without an ontology-based approach. Here, each artifact links against its own model of the system’s environment (its ontology). This is, however, highly detrimental to traceability as all four ontologies – O_R for the requirements, O_S for the system, and their formalized versions, \hat{O}_R and \hat{O}_S – are unconnected and thus may diverge. For example, requirements engineers can not trace their specification to legal definitions and certification authorities can not check whether the environment model used during verification is consistent with the assumptions of the requirement engineers. Even worse, results from the verification tools are potentially faulty, as the isolated ontologies may be inconsistent with each other. While verifiers guarantee results to be valid for the checked ontologies \hat{O}_R and \hat{O}_S , it can neither be ensured that the original ontologies O_R and O_S are consistent nor that the derived ontologies \hat{O}_R and \hat{O}_S represent the intended meaning of O_R and O_S . Essentially, we can not ensure a formal connection between \hat{O}_R and \hat{O}_S . If, for example, \hat{O}_R assigns a narrower semantics to a concept than O_R does, verification results are only applicable to the narrow semantics and are not transferable to the real world – an issue that can even remain undiscovered and thus become a traceability concern that, eventually, hinders type approval.

The problem of having scattered, unconnected ontologies leading to inconsistencies and untraceable derivations during systems engineering is addressed by *ontology-based systems engineering* (OBSE) [4, 8]. In general, OBSE iteratively refines a central ontology based on input of all relevant stakeholders to ensure traceability between all engineering steps. An integration of OBSE in our formal methods workflow yields the model scheme of Figure 2. Here, a central, informal domain conceptualization, O , is formalized as an ontology \hat{O} , which is accessed by every involved artifact. Since O arises from discussions during,

Fig. 2. Formal models for requirements R and systems S with an ontology-centric approach, creating a unified formal model \hat{O} from a single ontology O .

e.g., requirements engineering and product design, formal methods now use an ontology directly connected to prior engineering steps. Through this connection, we can trace the semantics of \hat{O} used during verification back to its origins. This increased traceability aids with the trust placed in the formal methods results – for type approval, it can now be reconstructed under which assumptions on the system’s environment the verifiers operated and how they were derived.

Our presentation gives an illustration on how such a connection might be achieved. We do so by means of a formal methods workflow for traffic rule assurance in ADSs, on which we reported prior experience [7]. Our proposed example traffic rule is based on §19 of the German road traffic act, which restricts behavior at railroad crossings within special areas and prescribes moderate speeds when approaching such crossings. We start by acknowledging the different mental models of legal experts, regulators, engineers, and society, e.g., on the meaning of ‘moderate speed’ and ‘special railroad areas’. For example, legally, the latter can include port roads, but only if they are appropriately marked. Once a semantics is agreed upon, a formal ontology can be created. A standard formalism is Description Logics (DLs) [1], which will be shortly introduced in the presentation. We continue to show an example of integrating DL ontologies into formal requirement languages by Temporal Conjunctive Queries, an LTL_f derivative [6]. Our example traffic rule can be formalized as the (highly simplified) requirement

$$\diamond((\text{SpecialRailroadArea}(\text{area}) \wedge \text{Approach}(\text{sys}, \text{area})) \rightarrow \text{ModerateSpeed}(\text{sys})).$$

Here, `SpecialRailroadArea` links to the semantics provided by the central, formal ontology \hat{O} . The same can be done for the system model, e.g., to also consider port roads as possible system inputs. We are aware of only few works on ontology-based system specification languages [2,3] and hope to use the track for inspiration and discussion. By specifying both models in an ontology-based manner, the final verification verdict can, in fact, be trusted to apply to the semantics intended by the legal experts, e.g., including port roads. In case questions arise during final type approval, the semantics of `SpecialRailroadArea` employed by *all* tools can be traced back to a single source – the ontology.

To summarize, our presentation will a) show how ontologies as a central model can be connected to formal methods b) highlight how this improves traceability and strengthens formal methods results for systems in complex contexts and c) aim at initiating a discussion on how other model-based approaches for engineering of AI-based systems might benefit from an ontology-centric view.

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